

Determination of Activity Coefficient of Cerium Nitrate from Diffusion Coefficient at 35°

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THERE are a number of well known methods by which activity coefficients of electrolytes in dilute solution can be precisely determined. The determination of activity coefficients from diffusion coefficients of univalent electrolytes at low concentrations, suggested by Harned¹, provides a less explored approach especially for electrolytes of higher valence types. The present communication reports the activity coefficients of an electrolyte of 3:1 type, viz. Ce(NO₃)₃ in dilute aqueous solutions.

Experimental

The diffusion coefficients of aqueous cerium nitrate in the concentration range 0.01–0.1 M, determined at 35° from the diaphragm-cell technique^{2–11}, are taken from the literature¹² and used in the present study. These are recorded in Table 1. The values of activity coefficient are given in Table 2.

where D is the diffusion coefficient, ν is number of ions into which the electrolyte molecule dissociates, R is the gas constant in ergs mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and T the absolute temperature. $\bar{m}/C$ is the concentration dependent mobility term and $\left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C}\right)$ is the thermodynamic term. The equations for computing the term $\bar{m}/C$ are discussed elsewhere¹². The diffusion coefficients in the concentration range 0.01–0.1 M, together with the electrophoretic terms ($\Delta \bar{m}'$) and ($\Delta \bar{m}''$) needed for finding $\bar{m}/C$ are, however, reproduced in Table 1. The rearrangement of equation (1) gives

$$\frac{D}{1000 \nu RT (\bar{m}/C)} - 1 = D' = C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \quad (2)$$

which defines the function of D' . The concentration C and $y_{\pm}$, the activity coefficient are in the same molar concentration scale. From equation (2) we get,

$$\ln y_{\pm} = \int_0^C \frac{D'}{C} dC = \int_0^C \frac{2D'}{C^{1/2}} dC^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\log y_{\pm} = \frac{\ln y_{\pm}}{2.3026} = 0.8686 \int_0^C \frac{D'}{C^{1/2}} dC^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

The value of $D'/C^{1/2}$ may be evaluated at the limit since the theoretical limiting slope of equation (5)

TABLE 1—COMPUTATION OF $D'/C^{1/2}$ USED FOR DETERMINING ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT OF CERIUM NITRATE* AT 35°

Concn. (C) mol dm ⁻³	D_{obs} × 10 ⁶	$-(\Delta \bar{m}'/C)$ × 10 ¹¹	$\Delta \bar{m}''/C$ × 10 ¹¹	$(\bar{m}/C)$ × 10 ¹⁰	$-D'$	$\sqrt{C}$	$-D'/\sqrt{C}$
0.01	1.888 9	0.002 3	5.759 3	285.579	0.627 90	0.100 0	6.279
0.02	1.012 3	0.002 9	6.945 4	297.434	0.667 89	0.141 4	4.723
0.03	0.973 5	0.003 2	7.465 4	302.631	0.686 11	0.173 2	3.961
0.04	0.905 7	0.003 2	7.789 7	305.871	0.711 06	0.200 0	3.555
0.05	0.908 9	0.003 7	8.007 9	308.057	0.712 09	0.223 6	3.185
0.06	0.835 1	0.003 8	8.066 9	308.640	0.735 97	0.244 9	3.005
0.07	0.848 7	0.003 9	8.082 5	308.795	0.731 81	0.264 6	2.766
0.08	0.873 6	0.004 1	8.095 9	308.927	0.724 06	0.282 8	2.560
0.09	0.962 6	0.004 2	8.109 1	309.058	0.696 07	0.300 0	2.320
0.10	1.277 4	0.004 3	8.029 8	308.264	0.595 64	0.316 2	1.884

* $S(t) = 3.8124$, $\epsilon = 75.04$, $\eta_0 = 7.194 \times 10^{-3}$, $\lambda_+^0 = 249.5$, $\lambda_-^0 = 85.48$.

TABLE 2—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT OF CERIUM NITRATE IN DILUTE AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 35°

C	0.000 1	0.000 4	0.000 9	0.001 6	0.002 5	0.003 6	0.004 9	0.006 4	0.008 1	0.010 0
$y_{\pm}$	0.861 6	0.745 2	0.647 3	0.564 4	0.494 1	0.434 3	0.383 2	0.339 6	0.302 1	0.269 9

Theory: The Onsager–Fuoss¹³ theory provides a relation (equation 1) by which the diffusion coefficient of electrolytes can be precisely determined. This relation has been made the basis for computing the activity coefficient.

$$D = 1000 \nu RT \left(\frac{\bar{m}}{C} \right) \left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \right) \quad (1)$$

is known,

$$\log f_{\pm} = -S(t) \sqrt{C} \quad (5)$$

where,

$$S(t) = \frac{1}{\nu} \left(\sum_1^b \nu_j Z_j^2 \right)^{1/2} \cdot \frac{1.290 \times 10^6}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}}$$

Thus

$$\lim_{c \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{D'}{C^{1/2}} = \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{2 \partial C^{1/2}} = \frac{2.3026 \partial \log y_{\pm}}{2 \partial C^{1/2}} \right. \\ \left. = -\frac{2.3026}{2} S_{(r)} \right] \quad (6)$$

By plotting $D'/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ to this limiting value, the activity coefficient can be computed from equation (4) by graphical integration method.

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Ultrasonic Velocity of Calcium Soap Solutions

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THE ultrasonic measurements have been used for determining the ion-solvent interaction and solvation number¹⁻⁵ in aqueous media but less attention has been paid to the solvation of ions in non-aqueous media.

The present work deals with the ultrasonic measurements of the solutions of calcium soaps (caprate and laurate) in a mixture of 50% chloroform and 50% propylene glycol (v/v) and the results have been used to calculate the various acoustical and physicochemical parameters of these soap solutions.

Experimental

Calcium soaps were prepared by the metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap with aqueous solution of calcium acetate. The purity of the soaps was checked by determining their melting points and elemental analysis.

The ultrasonic velocity was determined by Ultrasonic Interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at a frequency of 4 MHz with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$ at $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The densities of the solvent and solutions of calcium soaps were determined by means of a pycnometer.

The specific acoustic impedance⁶ (Z), intermolecular free length⁷ (L_f), adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_k), apparent molal volume⁸ (ϕ_v), molar sound velocity (R) and primary solvation number⁹ (S_n) have been calculated by using the relationships,

$$Z = \rho v \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = v^{-2} \rho^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$L_f = K \sqrt{\beta} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_k = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0\beta - \beta_0\rho) + \frac{\beta_0 M}{\rho_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0 - \rho) + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (5)$$

$$R = \frac{\overline{M}}{\rho} v^{1/3} \quad (6)$$

$$\overline{M} = \frac{n_0 M_0 + nM}{n_0 + n}$$

$$S_n = \frac{n_0}{n} \left[1 - \frac{V\beta}{n_0 V_0 \beta_0} \right] \quad (7)$$

where, ρ_0, ρ ; β_0, β ; n_0, n ; M_0, M and V_0 and V are the density, adiabatic compressibility, number of mole, molecular weight and molar volume of solvent and solute, respectively, and K, C and v are the temperature dependent Jacobson's constant, concentration (g mol dm⁻³) and ultrasonic velocity, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The results of ultrasonic velocity and various acoustical parameters for the solutions of calcium soaps in a mixture of 50% chloroform and 50% propylene glycol are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The variation of ultrasonic velocity with concentration is

$$(dv/dc) = -v/2[1/\rho(d\rho/dc) + 1/\beta(d\beta/dc)]$$

The negative values of $1/\beta(d\beta/dc)$ are higher than positive values of $1/\rho(d\rho/dc)$ for the solutions of calcium soaps, (dv/dc) is positive which is in agreement with the results of other workers¹⁰⁻¹² reported for electrolytic solutions.

The plots of v, β, L_f and Z vs C , soap concentration, are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a concentration which corresponds to the critical micelle concentration, (CMC) of calcium soaps (caprate = $12.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and laurate = $8.4 \times 10^{-3} M$). The variation of ultrasonic velocity